

Nuclear-Absorption Chiller Systems for Data Centers: A Mechanistic Approach to Design Space Evaluation

So-Bin Cho^{1,*}, Md Akhlak Bin Aziz^{1,2}, Ben Lindley^{1,3}, Timothy P. Grunloh², Caleb Brooks², Nicolas E. Stauff¹

¹ Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, IL; ² University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, Champaign, IL;

³ University of Wisconsin-Madison, Madison

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a mechanistic assessment of nuclear-powered data centers using steam-driven absorption chiller technology for waste heat recovery and cooling. A parameterized modeling approach evaluates two reactor technologies (pressurized water reactor (PWR) and sodium fast reactor (SFR)) coupled with single-, double-, and triple-effect LiBr-H₂O absorption chillers, comparing their performance against conventional electric chiller baselines. Performance is quantified using the peak IT load-to-reactor capacity ratio (PIR), a fundamental metric enabling technology-agnostic comparisons. Insights from PWR and SFR can be extended to PWR-type SMRs or high-temperature gas reactors (HTGR) with similar outlet temperatures to SFR. Results establish that nuclear-integrated absorption cooling achieves 7–8% higher PIR than electric chiller baselines across the examined reactor types. Operational sensitivity analyses examine realistic deployment considerations to support flexible siting and configurations: (1) temperature drops between extraction and generator inlet (0–20°C) cause minimal PIR degradation (<2%); (2) compared to individual condenser configurations (two condensers dedicated to reactor system and absorption chillers), shared configuration brings 0–4% PIR gains. The developed framework supports reactor-sizing and data center cooling system design decisions. The PIR metric connects design with investment decisions, yielding approximately \$0.1 million avoided reactor capital per 1 MWe of IT load for each +1 percentage-point of PIR (assuming \$10,000/kWe). Results represent upper bounds on absorption-cooling potential. Detailed thermal modeling will refine these bounds, but directional insights remain transferable.

Keywords: absorption chiller, advanced reactor, data center cooling system, nuclear cogeneration, waste heat recovery

1. INTRODUCTION

Data centers have emerged as critical infrastructure underpinning the modern digital economy, yet their escalating energy demands pose unprecedented challenges for power systems worldwide. Global data center electricity consumption is projected to nearly double by 2030, adding 340–540 TWh annually. The U.S. is experiencing a rapid increase in energy demand from data centers (DCs), with recent projections indicating a total increase of 26–85 GWy(e) by 2028 [1]. The rapid expansion challenges existing grid infrastructure, as these facilities require reliable, continuous power delivery at scales that strain regional transmission and distribution systems [1]. This challenge is amplified by a timing gap: DCs can be operational within 1–3 years, while supporting power plants and transmission upgrades take 5–10 years to complete [2].

The problem extends beyond capacity alone. Mission-critical data centers require 99.999% uptime (Tier IV standards), necessitating firm, dispatchable power that variable renewable sources cannot reliably

*chos@anl.gov

provide without massive overbuilding and storage [3]. Additionally, AI training clusters introduce rapid power oscillations of tens to hundreds of megawatts, creating new grid stability challenges [4]. These combined factors—capacity constraints, reliability requirements, and power quality concerns—necessitate innovative solutions that can provide both electricity and cooling efficiently. Nuclear energy aligns exceptionally well with DC operational requirements, offering carbon-free baseload power with inherent reliability that reduces backup system requirements [5, 6].

Data center cooling typically consumes 30–50% of facility electricity, with conventional electric chillers achieving coefficients of performance (COP) of 5–7 [7]. This substantial cooling load motivates consideration of absorption chillers, which convert thermal energy directly to cooling without the intermediate electricity conversion step. While absorption chillers have lower COPs (0.7–1.8) than electric chillers, they can utilize nuclear waste heat that would otherwise be rejected, potentially increasing the total IT load supportable per unit of reactor capacity.

Nuclear-data center integration must accommodate diverse deployment scenarios and regional variations. Data centers may be co-located with reactors for maximum efficiency or separated by several kilometers due to siting constraints, introducing thermal losses between heat extraction and chiller inlet. Additionally, absorption chillers integrated within data center cooling systems may share condensers with the nuclear plant or operate independently, each configuration offering distinct trade-offs.

This study's mechanistic framework systematically evaluates these deployment variations, by parameterizing key operational variables: (1) temperature drops from thermal losses between heat extraction and chiller inlet of 0–20°C (representing co-location to distant siting) and (2) absorption chiller condenser temperatures of 33°C and 39°C (covering independent condensers at 33°C with reactor-specific setpoints, and shared condenser designs at 39°C). Thus, the framework provides performance predictions applicable across diverse geographic regions and integration architectures, enabling site-specific optimization while maintaining broad applicability.

The framework provides distinct advantages for general applicability to other heat source by parameterizing the interface through absorption chiller COP curves and electricity penalties (from heat extraction). Since performance boundaries use validated balance-of-plant (BOP) data, findings extend to any reactor with similar thermal characteristics, such as outlet temperature and cycle efficiency.

2. METHODS

Rather than providing individual use-case evolutions, the framework developed establishes performance relationships between reactor characteristics, absorption chiller configurations, and operational conditions. This approach ensures findings remain applicable across technology variants—for instance, any reactor achieving similar outlet temperatures to the PWR or SFR can leverage these results for preliminary performance estimation.

2.1. Key Assumptions and Upper-Bound Analysis

Several deliberate assumptions establish the framework's scope and applicability. The framework assumes heat can be extracted at any target temperature without steam mixing constraints, establishing theoretical upper bounds for absorption chiller performance. While actual implementations must account for steam extraction points, these upper bounds provide valuable targets for system optimization and technology selection. The model employs steady-state calculations sufficient for differentiating performance across reactor-chiller combinations. Thus, the analysis focuses on how switching to absorption chillers would impact reactor sizing.

The analysis assumes no grid imports for primary power, with reactors sized to meet peak DC demand. This conservative approach ensures findings remain valid for behind-the-meter (BTM) configurations and allow straightforward adjustment for grid-connected scenarios. *Figure 1* illustrates the nuclear-powered DC equipped with an absorption-chiller-based cooling system. Heat for cooling is supplied via turbine steam extraction or direct bypass to meet absorption-chiller setpoints (in terms of inlet steam temperature and pressure). This configuration assumes heat extraction, delivered directly to the generator (absorption chiller). UPS bridges outages for ride-through or safe shutdown. An electric chiller configuration is included for baseline comparison (not illustrated in *Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Nuclear power plant (NPP)–data center (DC) integration via absorption chiller-based cooling

2.2. Data Center Demand Profiles

The total electrical demand of a nuclear-powered DC is modeled as the sum of five components:

$$P_{DC}(t) = P_{IT}(t) + P_{UPS}(t) + P_{ch}(t) + P_{aux} + P_{LT} \quad (1)$$

where $P_{IT}(t)$ denotes the instantaneous computational load of servers and networking equipment; $P_{UPS}(t)$ captures conversion or no-load losses in the uninterruptible power supply; $P_{ch}(t)$ represents the direct-cooling demand met by the chiller plant; P_{aux} aggregates auxiliary cooling power (CRAH fans, chilled-water pumps, cooling-tower fans); and P_{LT} reflects building lighting. Consistent with facility practice for 24/7 operation, P_{aux} and P_{LT} are modeled as time-invariant constant. Total site cooling duty considers IT-load plus conversion losses (1 MWe = 1 MWt):

$$P_{ch}(t) = \frac{P_{IT}(t) + P_{UPS}(t)}{COP} \quad (2)$$

where COP is the coefficient of performance of chiller system, defined as the ratio of useful cooling provided to electrical input power. The term $P_{IT}(t) + P_{UPS}(t)$ represents the site-wide sensible load that must be removed from the IT equipment and UPS losses. For the baseline case, electric chiller COP is set at 5.2. UPS sized to 1.32x IT load peak (P_{IT}^{peak}) with 97% AC-DC conversion efficiency. Detailed UPS loss characteristics are provided in [8].

Auxiliary cooling is modeled as fixed fractions of peak IT load: 10% for computer-room air-handling (CRAH) fans, 5% for chilled-water distribution pumps, and 1% for cooling-tower fans. Lighting is represented as 1% of average IT load [9]. The baseline reactor is sized to cover the coincident peak of all five components in Eq. 1 at the IT load peak, plus reactor-specific house loads (Appendix Table A 1)

2.3. Rapid-Assessment Framework

The rapid-assessment framework determines the minimum thermal reactor capacity required to meet peak DC demand and evaluates PIR value for each reactor-chiller combination. To identify optimal operating points, the tool implements a temperature scan over each reactor's feasible steam extraction temperature range in one-degree increments. At each temperature, the model reads COP values from

pre-compiled CSV files, computes the required thermal input, and calculates the extraction fraction relative to reference reactor capacity. Peak diverted reactor thermal power [MWt] is calculated using Eq. 2 with absorption chiller COP values.

The framework uses COP curves from Gomri's study [10] covering single- to triple-effect lithium bromide (LiBr) solution systems. *Figure 2* (left) shows the implemented COP curves [10] for condenser temperatures of 33°C and 39°C. Net plant electric output is evaluated using turbine-penalty correlations from prior research [11], expressed as a function of the fraction of maximum available heat extracted. *Figure 2* (right) shows the extraction-temperature envelopes for identifying favorable operating points. Both figures are linearly interpolated at 1°C increments from each source to enable continuous design space exploration. This framework assumes continuous turbine extraction (versus discrete commercial ports) Consequently, reported performance represents the thermodynamic upper bound assuming the BOP is optimized for thermal coupling.

Figure 2. Variation of the coefficient of performance (COP) for single-, double-, and triple-effect absorption chillers as a function of generator temperature (left) and impact of thermal-extraction rate on turbine electric output (right).

When replacing electric chillers with absorption systems, the reactor's available generation is reduced but electric chiller demand is eliminated. The net effect (Δ) represents the difference between lost generation and displaced electric chiller load in MWt. If $\Delta < 0$ (when displaced electric-chiller load exceeds the turbine penalty), the required reactor thermal capacity decreases. Finally, PIR is defined as the ratio of respective IT load to this required thermal capacity:

$$\text{PIR} = \frac{P_{IT}^{\text{peak}}}{Q_R + \Delta} \quad (3)$$

where Q_R is baseline reactor capacity [MWt] obtained from Section 2.2 (DC peak demand plus reactor house load).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rapid-assessment results focus on two design considerations for nuclear-powered absorption cooling systems: (1) the impact of heat-transport temperature drop between the reactor extraction point and the absorption-chiller generator inlet ($\Delta T = 0\text{--}20^\circ\text{C}$), and (2) the effect of coordinating condenser setpoints between the reactor and the absorption chiller.

3.1. Temperature Drop Effects and System Resilience

Temperature losses between reactor extraction points and absorption chiller generators, quantified as ΔT , arise from heat transport through piping networks and intermediate heat exchangers. Well-insulated piping systems typically experience thermal losses of approximately 0.3°C per kilometer for low- to mid-grade heat ($<150^\circ\text{C}$) [12]. Commercial-grade shell-and-tube heat exchangers operate with a minimum 5 K temperature difference (pinch point) between hot and cold sides [13]. Enhanced insulation can mitigate these losses but increases capital expenditure (CAPEX), with costs comparable to those in nuclear cogeneration systems [14]. Under the assumption of co-located heat delivery ($\Delta T = 0^\circ\text{C}$) and a stable 9% daily IT-load swing, absorption cooling outperforms the electric-chiller reference for both PWR and SFR cases by 7.4% and 6.8%, respectively.

As temperature drops increase, the framework identifies distinct optimization pathways for each reactor type. The PWR system transitions to triple-effect technology at $\Delta T = 20^\circ\text{C}$. The SFR maintains double-effect operation through $\Delta T = 10^\circ\text{C}$ before transitioning to single-effect at $\Delta T = 20^\circ\text{C}$. The PWR and SFR exhibit 2% and 1.7% decreases in PIR across the $0\text{--}20^\circ\text{C}$ range, and 0.8% and 1% decreases for the $0\text{--}10^\circ\text{C}$ range, respectively. Importantly, even at 20°C temperature drop, absorption chillers show $>4.8\%$ higher PIR than their respective baselines across PWR and SFR designs.

Figure 3. Impact of temperature drop between extraction and chiller inlet.

3.2. Condenser Integration Strategies

Condenser configurations of independent and combined operation at 39°C are evaluated in *Figure 4*. Under the baseline independent condenser configuration, absorption chillers operate at 33°C (*Figure 4* (left panel)), while reactor condensers are set to their typical design points (PWR: 43°C ; SFR: 46°C). The PWR and SFR systems achieve PIR improvements over baseline values of 7.0% and 7.7%, respectively.

Under the shared condenser configuration at 39°C —representing tightly coupled, co-located operations—the system exhibits competing thermal effects. The chiller's performance decreases 5.1% for PWR and 5.9% for SFR, while the absolute PIR increases 0-0.7%. The condenser arrangement creates opposing effects on the reactor BOP and the absorption chiller. As the chiller COP drops when its condenser temperature rises from 33°C to 39°C , the reactor benefits from a slightly cooler heat sink

(about 40°C to 39°C). These opposing effects largely offset each other, keeping PIR nearly unchanged and giving the coupled system resilience to varying ambient conditions across different designs.

Figure 4. . Condenser-temperature coordination between reactor and absorption chiller

4. CONCLUSION

This study establishes a mechanistic framework for evaluating nuclear-absorption chiller systems in DC applications. The parameterized approach demonstrates that nuclear-integrated absorption cooling achieves 7–8% higher peak IT load support than conventional electric cooling, with each percentage-point improvement yielding approximately \$0.1 million¹ in avoided reactor capital per MWe of IT load.

Findings establish clear design principles for nuclear-powered DC cooling. First, technology selection depends on the physical distance between reactor and absorption chiller. Double-effect chillers work best when temperature drops remain below 10°C. At larger separations causing 20°C drops, PWR systems shift to triple-effect technology while SFR systems adopt single-effect operation. Each reactor type selects its optimal configuration based on operating constraints. Second, condenser integration offers significant benefits for co-located facilities. Sharing condenser infrastructure between nuclear plants and data centers reduces capital costs while improving performance. This approach delivers consistent PIR improvements (5–8%) over respective baselines.

Results shown here represent upper bounds on absorption-cooling potential. Detailed thermal modeling will refine these bounds and enable optimizing an integrated nuclear BOP/chiller configuration. Thus, the findings remain useful for directional insights. Additionally, dynamic system modeling will be essential for control strategy development under variable loads.

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¹ Derived as $(1 - 1/1.01) \times \text{ReactorCost} [\text{USD/kWe}] \times 1000 \text{ kWe}/1 \text{ MWe}$; *ReactorCost* refers to the nuclear island only, excluding thermal transport infrastructure (e.g., piping).

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APPENDIX A

Table A 1. Reference reactor parameters and representative steam conditions adopted for rapid assessment of absorption-chiller integration.

	PWR	SFR
Reactor power [MWt]	1201	250
Net cycle efficiency	35.2%	42.0%
Considered steam temp. [°C]		
Main steam	273	500
HPT	241, 231, 207	290, 227
Intermediate steam	258	150
LPT	167, 128, 96, 76	101, 80
Condenser/Cooler	43	45
House load		
[% of reactor thermal power]	3%	3%

LPT, low-pressure turbine; HPT, high-pressure turbine

Reactor efficiency and steam-extraction information are from [11].